

Development And Validation Of Chromatographic Method For Simultaneous Estimation Of Efonidipine Hydrochloride Ethanolate, Telmisartan And Chlorthalidone In Synthetic Mixture.

Dhodi Drashti¹, Shuchi Desai^{*2}, Patel Aashiya³, Megha Shah³

¹Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, ROFEL Shri G.M. Bilakhia College of Pharmacy, Vapi, Gujarat, India.

²Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, C.K Pithawalla Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Research, Surat, Gujarat, India.

³Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, Laxminarayandev college of pharmacy, Bharuch, Gujarat, India.

ABSTRACT

Combination of Efonidipine Hydrochloride ethanolate, Telmisartan and Chlorthalidone is used in the treatment of diabetes. HPLC separation of EHE, TELMI and CHLOR was followed by detection of their spots at 210 nm. The separation was carried out on Shim-pack Solar C18 (250mm×4.6mm, 5µm) using mobile phase [Methanol: Acetonitrile: water (25:65:10 v/v) Whole mobile phase pH-4.5 with 1% OPA]. The linearity for EHE, TELMI and CHLOR were range between 1.6-8 µg/ml and 3.2-16µg/ml and 1-5 µg/ml respectively, with correlation coefficient 0.9996 and 0.9999 and 0.9995. All the developed methods were validated according to ICH guidelines. The developed methods were applied successfully for the Quantitative determination of EHE, TELMI and CHLOR.

Keywords: Area Under Curve method, RP-HPLC, Efonidipine hydrochloride ethanolate, Telmisartan, chlorthalidone.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most prevalent disorders is hypertension. Although it is not a disease, it poses a substantial risk for CVS mortality and morbidity. Although risk seems to increase even above 120/80 mm Hg, it can be defined as 140 mm Systolic and 90 mm Diastolic mm Hg. Majority of cases is primary hypertension and the causes are unknown. Renin angiotensin system may also contribute to tone of blood vessels in Hypertension. Antihypertensive drugs by lowering Blood pressure may reset the barostat to function at a lower level of blood pressure.^[1]

EFONIDIPINE HYDROCHLORIDE ETHANOLATE (EFO) used to reduce the automaticity of the heart and causes vasodilation by inhibiting the L- and T-type calcium channels. The

chronotropic effects of efonidipine cause a drop-in heart rate. Act as a Calcium channel blocker.^[2]

Telmisartan (TELM) binds reversibly and selectively to the receptors in vascular smooth muscle and the adrenal gland, interfering with the binding of angiotensin II to the angiotensin II AT1-receptor. Blocking the effects of angiotensin II lowers systemic vascular resistance because it is a vasoconstrictor that also increases aldosterone synthesis and release. Ion channels, other hormone receptors, or the angiotensin converting enzyme are not inhibited by telmisartan. Act as angiotensin II receptor antagonist.^[3]

CHLORTHALIDONE (CHLOR) is Thiazide-like Diuretic bind Through suppression of the Na⁺/Cl⁻ symporter in the cortical diluting section of the ascending limb of the loop of Henle, chlorthalidone prevents the reabsorption of sodium and chloride.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Reduced sodium reabsorption leads to an osmotic, sodium- driven diuresis, which in turn lowers extracellular fluid and plasma volume. Chlorthalidone indirectly increases potassium excretion by boosting sodium supply to the distal renal tubule through the sodium-potassium exchange pathway.^[4]

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Telmisartan and Efonidipine hydrochloride ethanolate was received as gift sample from Zuventus Pharma Pvt. Ltd, Pune, and Maharashtra.

Chlorthalidone was received as gift sample from CTX Life Science Private. Ltd, Surat. Methanol, OPA (UV Grade – Thomas Baker, Mumbai).

Acetonitrile, methanol, water (HPLC grade) – Rankem.

UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Double beam) (Shimadzu-1900i, Software-UV Probe, Version 2.42) having matched quartz cells of light path 1 cm was used.

High performance liquid chromatographic system (LC 2010 CHT) equipped with UV-visible detector was used for the analysis. The data were recorded using LC solution software.

- 1. Preparation of EFO standard stock solution:** (1000 µg/ml) Accurately weighed 8 mg of EFO and take into to 10 ml volumetric flask and it was dissolved in methanol and volume was make up to 10 ml with the methanol to get stock solution (800 µg/ml).
- 2. Preparation of EFO working stock solution:** (800 µg/ml) 1 ml Aliquot from above standard stock solution was pipetted out into 10 ml of volumetric flask and volume was make up to 10 ml with methanol to get a working solution 800 µg/ml.
- 3. Preparation of TELMI standard stock solution:** (1600 µg/ml) Accurately weighed 16 mg of TELMI and take to 10 ml volumetric flask and it was dissolved in methanol and volume was make up to 10 ml with the methanol to get stock solution (1600 µg/ml).

- 4. Preparation of TELMI working stock solution:** (160 µg/ml) 1 ml Aliquot from above standard stock solution was pipetted out into 10 ml of volumetric flask and volume was make up to 10 ml with methanol to get a working solution 160 µg/ml.
- 5. Preparation of CHLOR standard stock solution:** (1000 µg/ml) Accurately weighed 10 mg of CHLOR and take to 10 ml volumetric flask and it was dissolved in methanol and volume was make up to 10 ml with the methanol to get stock solution (1000 µg/ml).
- 6. Preparation of CHLOR working solution (100 µg/ml):** Aliquot of 1 ml from above standard stock solution was pipetted out into 10 ml of volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with methanol.
- 7. Preparation of Ternary mixture of EHE, TELMI and CHLOR:** Aliquots of 0.4 ml from working solution of EHE (80 µg/ml) and 0.4 ml from working solution of TELMI (160 µg/ml),) and 0.2 ml from working solution of CHLOR (100 µg/ml) were taken into common volumetric flask and diluted up to 10 ml with mobile phase to make final concentration EHE (3.2 µg/ml), TELMI (6.4 µg/ml), and CHLOR (2 µg/ml).

PREPARATION OF CALIBRATION CURVE:

- 1. Calibration curve for EFO:** Preparation of five different concentration of standard solution of EFO the range is 1.6- 8 µg/ml. The solution was prepared by pipette out 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1 ml from working stock solution of EFO (800 µg/ml) and take into series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and the volume was make up to 10 ml with methanol to produce 1.6, 3.2, 4.8, 6.4, 8 µg/ml respectively. Area under the curve of the prepared solution was measured at wavelength range (247-257 nm) against methanol used as blank. Calibration Curve was plotted at selected wavelength range and equation were obtained.
- 2. Calibration curve for TELMI:** Preparation of five different concentration of standard solution of TELMI range is 3.2-16 µg/ml. The solution was prepared by pipette out 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and

1 ml of working stock solution of TELMI (160 µg/ml) and take into series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and the volume was make up to 10 ml with methanol to produce 3.2, 6.4, 9.6, 12.8, 16 µg/ml respectively. The Area under the curve of the prepared solution was measured under wavelength range 224-233 nm against methanol used as blank. Calibration Curve was plotted at selected wavelength range and equation were obtained.

- 3. Calibration curve for CHLOR:** Preparation of five different concentrations of standard solution of CHLOR range is 1-5 µg/ml. The solution was prepared by pipette out 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 ml of working stock solution of CHLOR (100 µg/ml) and take into series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and the volume was make up to 10 ml with methanol to produce 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 µg/ml respectively. The Area under the curve of the prepared solution was measured under wavelength range 273-282 nm against methanol used as blank. Calibration Curve was plotted at selected wavelength range and equation were obtained.

VALIDATION OF PROPOSED METHOD:^[10]

- 1. Linearity (n=5):** Linearity response was estimated by analysis of five different levels of calibration curve in the range of 1.6-8 µg/ml for EFO and 3.2-16 µg/ml for TELMI And 1-5 µg/ml for CHLOR. The calibration curve plotted that is absorbance vs. concentration and correlation coefficient and regression line equations for EFO and TELMI and CHLOR were calculated.

2. Precision:

Repeatability (n=6): For EFO 0.6 ml taken working solution (800 µg/ml) and for TELMI 0.6 ml taken from working solution (160µg/ml) and for CHLOR 0.3 ml taken from working solution (100µg/ml) were transferred into the series of 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was make up to 10 to with methanol to get solution they containing 4.8 µg/ml,

9.6 µg/ml and 3 µg/ml of EFO, TELMI And CHLOR. Prepared solution analyses for six times (n=6) and Relative standard deviation (% R.S.D) was calculated.

Intraday Precision (n=3): Take 0.32, 0.48, 0.64 ml from working stock solution of EFO (100 µg/ml) were transferred into series of 10 ml volumetric flask. And take 0.64, 0.96 and 1.28 ml from working stock solution of TELMI (100µg/ml) And take 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 ml from workingstock solution of CHLOR (100µg/ml)were transferred into series of 10 ml volumetric flask volume was make up 10 ml with methanol to get a solution containing 3.2, 4.8 and 6.4 µg/ml of EFO and 6.4, 9.6 and 12.8 µg/ml of TELMI and 3, 4, and 5 µg/ml of CHLOR and analysis of solution for three times (n=3) on the same day within short interval of time and relative standard deviation (% R.S.D.) was calculated.

Interday Precision (n=3): Take 0.32, 0.48, 0.64 ml from working stock solution of EFO (100 µg/ml) were transferred into series of 10 ml volumetric flask. And take 0.64, 0.96 and 1.28 ml from working stock solution of TELMI (100µg/ml) And take 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 ml from workingstock solution of CHLOR (100µg/ml) were transferred into series of 10 ml volumetric flask volume was make up 10 ml with methanol to get a solution containing 3.2, 4.8 and 6.4 µg/ml of EFO and 6.4, 9.6 and 12.8 µg/ml of TELMI and 3, 4, and 5 µg/ml of CHLOR and Analysis of solution for three times (n=3) on the three different days and % R.S.D. was calculated.

3. Accuracy (n=3):

Preparation of synthetic mixture solution: A synthetic mixture containing 40 mg of TELMI equivalent was placed in a 10 ml volumetric flask. Methanol was introduced and sonicate for 2-3 min, and the volume was brought up to the mark. Whatman filter paper no. 42 was used to filter the mixture. As a result, the final solution included 1000 µg/ml TELMI, 1000 µg/ml EHE and 1000 µg/ml CHLOR. to make a solution containing TELMI (100 µg/ml), EHE (100 µg/ml) and CHLOR (100 µg/ml) 1.0 ml of the above solution was pipette out and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask, where the amount was made up to the mark with methanol. Each solution was scanned from 200-400 nm against methanol as a black. Absorbance of solution was measured at selected wavelength for EHE, TELMI and CHLOR. The amount of EHE, TELMI and CHLOR was calculated at each level (80 %, 100%,

and 120%) and % recoveries were calculated. (Table I).

- 4. DL and QL:** (Detection limit) was estimated from the set of 5 calibration curves that were used to determine linearity of the method. The LOD was calculated by using the formula:

$$DL = 3.3 \times S.D./Slope$$

Where, S.D. = Standard deviation of the Y – intercepts of 5 calibration curves

Slope = Mean slope of 5 calibration curves The QL (Quantitation limit) was estimated from the set of 5 calibration curves that were used to determine linearity of the method.

$$QL = 10 \times S.D./Slope$$

Where, S.D. = Standard deviation of the Y – intercepts of 5 calibration curves Slope = Mean slope of 5 calibration curves.

- 5. System Suitability studies:** Evaluation of system suitability was done by analysing six replicates of EHE, TELMI and CHLOR in a mixture at concentration of 3.2 µg/ml of EHE and 6.4 µg/ml of TELMI and µg/ml of CHLOR. The column efficiency, peak asymmetry and resolution were calculated for each replicate.

Specificity: Specificity involves quantitative detection of analyte in the presence of those components that may be expected to be part of sample matrix. Specificity of developed method was established by spiking of EHE, TELMI and CHLOR in hypothetical placebo (i.e. might be expected to be present) and expressing that analytes peak were not interfered from excipients.

- 6. Robustness:** Robustness of the method was determined by subjecting the method to slight change in the method condition like,

- Mobile Phase Ratio
- Flow Rate

Three replicates were prepared for the same of Concentration 1.6 µg/ml for EHE and 3.2 µg/ml for

TELMi and 1 µg/ml for CHLOR and % R.S.D. was calculated.

- 7. Simultaneous estimation of Efonidipine Hydrochloride Ethanolate, Telmisartan and Chlorthalidone in Combine Dosage Form by RP-HPLC method:** A synthetic mixture containing 40 mg of TELMI equivalent was placed in a 10 ml volumetric flask. Methanol was introduced and sonicate for 2-3 min, and the volume was brought up to the mark. Whatman filter paper no. 42 was used to filter the mixture. As a result, the final solution included 1000 µg/ml TELMI, 1000µg/ml EHE and 1000 µg/ml CHLOR. to make a solution containing TELMI (100 µg/ml), EHE (100 µg/ml) and CHLOR (100 µg/ml) 1.0 ml of the above solution was pipette out and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask, where the amount was made up to the mark with methanol. The concentration of Telmi, EHE, and CHLOR was obtained from the calibration curve. Amount of Telmi, EHE, and CHLOR was calculated.

RESULTS:

SELECTION OF ELUTION MODE: Reverse phase chromatography was chosen because of the recommended use for ionic and moderate to non-polar compound. Reverse phase chromatography is not only simple, convenient but also better in terms of efficiency, stability and reproducibility. C18 column was selected because it is least polar compound to C4 and C8 column. C18 column allows elution of polar compound. In addition to this, UV detector is used, which allows easy detection of the compounds in UV transparent organic solvents. A 250 mm ×4.6 mm column packed with 5µm particles was preferred as a starting point for method development. Isocratic mode was chosen due to simplicity in application and robustness with respect to longer column stability. This configuration provides a large value for the number of theoretical plates giving better separation. (Table I).

SELECTION OF MOBILE PHASE: The mobile phase should be sufficiently transparent at the detection of wavelength. Methanol, Acetonitrile and water (pH 4.5 adjusted with ortho phosphoric acid) are the solvent used for mobile phase provided optimum polarity for proper separation and resolution

for Efonidipine Hydrochloride Ethanolate, Telmisartan and Chlorthalidone. The ratio selected is Methanol: Acetonitrile and water (whole MP pH 4.5 adjusted with orthophosphoric acid) 25:65:10 v/v/v.^(Fig.1)

Validation Parameters:

Linearity: A linearity range for Efonidipine, Telmisartan and Chlorthalidone was found to be in the range, 1.6- $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 3.2-16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1-5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ are shown in **fig.III, IV, V and VI**.

Precision: Reproducibility: A reproducibility range for Efonidipine, Telmisartan and Chlorthalidone was found to be in the range i.e. RSD is less than 2. ^(Table II). Also interday and intraday precision data shows results within the limit. ^(Table III).

Accuracy: Accuracy of the proposed method was assured by performing recovery study from synthetic mixture at three level by standard addition method. Percentage recovery for EHE, TELMI and CHLOR was obtained respectively. The results are depicted in table no. Recovery was found be in the limit of 98-102 %. ^(Table IV).

System suitability: System suitability data were checked by different parameters of method like retention time, theoretical plate, tailing factor and resolution. RSD was found less than 2%. ^(Table V).

Specificity: Method was determined by analyzing standard drugs and sample of EFO, TELMI and CHLOR. The results suggested that proposed method is specific, the excipients present in the marketed formulation does not affect the result. The chromatogram taken by running only with the mobile phase, placebo and after injection of the sample are given in **figure VII and VIII**.

DL and QL: It was discovered that the DL for EHE, TELMI, and CHLOR were 0.1397g/ml, 0.102376 g/ml, and 0.10456 g/ml, respectively.

QL for EHE, TELMI, and CHLOR were 0.4236 g/ml, 0.0.3102 g/ml, and 0.3168 g/ml.

Robustness: By purposefully changing the following method parameters, the robustness of the method was determined.^(Table VI, VII, VIII).

- Flow rate: ± 0.2 units
- Mobile Phase Ratio: ± 2.0

Analysis of Synthetic mixture: Suitability of the method was tested by analysing the synthetic mixture. The data of assay for synthetic mixture is shown in **table IX**.

CONCLUSION:

The method has linearity in the range of 1.6-8 g/ml for EFO, 3.2-16 g/ml for TELMI, and 1-5 g/ml for CHLOR, according to the results of the analysis of EFO, TELMI, and CHLOR in their tablet dosage form using the RP-HPLC Method. For EFO, TELMI, and CHLOR at 210 nm, the correlation coefficient (r) was found to be 0.9996 and the regression coefficient (R²) was found to be 0.9993, 0.9998, and 0.9991, respectively. EFO, TELMI, and CHLOR were found to have limits of detection of 0.1496 g/ml, 0.3292g/ml, and 0.1045 g/ml, respectively. EFO, TELMI, and CHLOR each had a limit of quantification of 0.4534 g/ml, 0.9978 g/ml, and 0.3168 g/ml, respectively. The % assay was determined to be 99.03% w/w for EFO, 99.3% w/w for TELMI, and 98.85% w/w for CHLOR, respectively. Additionally, it was discovered that the R.S.D. for precision, intraday, and intraday study was less than 2%.

Figure I: Overlain spectra of EFO, TELMI, And CHLOR for selection of wavelength

Figure II: Chromatogram of EHE, TELMI and CHLOR in Methanol: ACN:Water (25:65:10 v/v) (whole M.P pH-4.5 adjusted with 1% OPA)

Figure III: Overlain Chromatogram of EHE (1.6-8 µg/ml), TELMI (3.2-16 µg/ml) and CHLOR (1-5 µg/ml)

Figure IV: Calibration Curve of EHE

Figure V: Calibration curve of TELMI

Figure VI: Calibration curve of CHLOR

Figure VII: Chromatogram of Placebo and mobile phase

Figure VIII: Chromatogram of sample (synthetic mixture)

Table I: Optimized chromatographic condition:

Sr. NO	PARAMETER	CONDITION
1	Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water: methanol (65:25:10 % v/v/v)
2	Flow rate	1.0 ml / min
3	Run time	10 min
4	Volume of injection	10 μ l
5	Detection Wavelength	210 nm
6	Diluent	Mobile phase

Table II: Repeatability data for EHE, TELMI, and CHLOR

Drug	Concentration (μ g/ml)	Mean Peak Area \pm S.D. (n=6)	% R.S.D
EHE	4.8	361733.3 \pm 939.21	0.2596
TELM	9.6	764086.7 \pm 2122.91	0.2778
CHLOR	3	343293.3 \pm 2237.4	0.6517

Table III: Intra/Interday precision for EHE, TELMI and CHLOR

Drug	Concentration (μ g/ml)	Mean Peak Area \pm S.D. (n=6) (Intraday Precision)	% R.S. D	Mean Peak Area \pm S.D. (n=6)	% R.S.D
EHE	3.2	282271.3 \pm 1112.88	0.3942	282893.3 \pm 1438.31	0.5084
	4.8	362244 \pm 1190.32	0.3285	362442 \pm 1497.95	0.4132
	6.4	454260.6 \pm 1823.66	0.4014	452291 \pm 2125.83	0.4700
TELM	6.4	684461.3 \pm 2562.35	0.3743	684603.3 \pm 2911.70	0.4253
	9.6	762764 \pm 222.11	0.2911	763856.3 \pm 2219.64	0.2905
	12.8	834749 \pm 1537.42	0.1841	836109.3 \pm 1777.52	0.2125
CHLOR	2	252591.3 \pm 2213.96	0.8765	253861 \pm 2543.13	1.0019
	3	343261.6 \pm 2330.0	0.6787	346409.3 \pm 2565.20	0.7405
	4	425627 \pm 1911.74	0.4491	426084.3 \pm 2188.52	0.5136

Table IV: Accuracy data for EHE, TELMI and CHLOR

Drug	Level	Amount of sample (µg/ml)	Amount of std spiked (µg/ml)	Total amount	Amount of sample found (µg/ml)	Mean % Recovery ± S.D. (n=3)
EHE	0 %	3.2	0	3.2	3.18	99.37
	80 %	3.2	2.56	5.76	5.79	100.52
	100 %	3.2	3.2	6.4	6.41	100.15
	120 %	3.2	3.84	7.04	7.1	99.57
TELM I	0 %	6.4	0	6.4	6.39	99.84
	80 %	6.4	5.12	11.52	11.56	100.34
	100 %	6.4	6.4	12.08	12.7	99.21
	120 %	6.4	7.68	14.08	14.12	100.28
CHLOR	0 %	2	0	2	1.99	99.5
	80 %	2	1.6	3.6	3.61	100.27
	100 %	2	2	4	4.01	100.25
	120 %	2	2.4	4.4	4.37	99.31

Table V: System suitability data

Drugs	Parameters	Mean ± S.D. (n=6)	%R.S. D
EHE	Retention Time	4.7635 ± 0.011	0.2500
	Theoretical Plate	28984.85 ± 104.24	0.3596
	Tailing Factor	1.453833 ± 0.0030	0.2105
	Resolution	3.752833 ± 0.0037	0.1002
TELM I	Retention Time	3.717 ± 0.0079	0.2138
	Theoretical Plate	20255.37 ± 77.057	0.3804
	Tailing Factor	1.7645 ± 0.0037	0.2143
	Resolution	3.508 ± 0.0048	0.1384
CHLOR	Retention Time	2.891167 ± 0.0060	0.2091
	Theoretical Plate	22606.71 ± 98.26	0.4346
	Tailing Factor	1.453 ± 0.0031	0.2176

Table VI: Robustness data for EHE

Parameter	Level	Mean peak Area ± S.D.(n=3)	% R.S. D	Rt ± S.D. (n=3)	%R.S.D.
Mobile phase	23:67:10% V/V/V	207494.7 ± 679.30	0.3273	4.764 ± 0.0145	0.304908

	27:63:10% V/V/V	207553.3 ± 852.48	0.4107	4.77 ± 0.01314	0.275477
Flow Rate	0.8 ml/min.	207544.3 ± 661.40	0.3186	4.726 ± 0.01113	0.235623
	1.2 ml/min.	207630 ± 921.48	0.4438	4.722 ± 0.01473	0.311964

Table VII: Robustness data for TELMI

Parameter	Level	Mean peak Area ± S.D. (n=3)	% R.S. D	Rt ± S.D. (n=3)	%R.S.D.
Mobile phase	23:67:10 % V/V/V	768091.3±1848.53	0.2406	3.723 ±0.0080	0.2170
	27:63:10 % V/V/V	767332.3 ± 1383.09	0.180248	3.73 ±0.0045	0.1218
Flow Rate	0.8 ml/min.	767348 ± 767348	0.226645	3.779 ±0.0116	0.3089
	1.2 ml/min.	767209.7 ± 1772.62	0.231048	3.780 ±0.0085	0.2249

Table VIII: Robustness data for CHLOR

Parameter	Level	Mean peak Area ± S.D. (n=3)	% R.S.D	Rt ± S.D. (n=3)	%R.S.D.
Mobile phase	23:67:10%V/V/V	254707.3 ± 871.5603	0.3421	2.893 ±0.00721	0.24926
	23:67:10%V/V/V	254744.7 ± 905.03	0.3552	2.889 ± 0.01006	0.34836
Flow Rate	0.8 ml/min.	254675.3 ± 904.47	0.3551	2.721 ± 0.00832	0.30594
	1.2 ml/min.	254827 ± 1020.337	0.4004	2.78 ±0.00556	0.2002

Table IX: Determination of Assay of EFO, TELMI and CHLOR

Synthetic mixture	Amount taken (mg/tablet)			Amount Obtained (mg/tablet)			% EFO ± S. D (n=3)	% TELMI ± S. D (n=3)	% CHLOR ± S. D (n=3)
	EHE	TEL	CHLOR	EHE	TEL	CHLOR			
	20	40	12.5	19.95	39.72	12.40	99.76 ± 0.0351	99.3 ± 0.3605	99.2 ± 0.2771

Conflict of interest:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this article.

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HOW TO CITE: Dhodi Drashti, Shuchi Desai, Patel Aashiya, Megha Shah, Development And Validation Of Chromatographic Method For Simultaneous Estimation Of Efonidipine Hydrochloride Ethanolate, Telmisartan And Chlorthalidone In Synthetic Mixture, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (4), 1958-1968. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19715668>

